

The Socio-Economic Landscape of Walking: Longitudinal Insights from the UK National Travel Survey (2007-2023)

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Summary

Walking is a sustainable transport mode with significant health, environmental, and socio-economic benefits. This study investigates the socio-economic factors associating with walking behaviours in England, using National Travel Survey data (2007–2023). Results show increased walking participation over time. Urban residents and individuals with higher income and education levels walked more, while those with mobility difficulties were significantly less likely to walk. In contrast, lower-income individuals walked more often, partly due to limited access to private vehicles. The findings reveal emphasise the need for inclusive policies and targeted investments to promote equitable and sustainable walking.

KEYWORDS: Walking behaviour, Active travel, Socio-economic determinants, Mobility Inequality

1. Introduction

Walking is increasingly recognised as a cornerstone of active transport, contributing significantly to public health, environmental sustainability, and social equity. As an accessible, affordable, and environmentally friendly form of travel, walking supports physical and mental well-being while requiring minimal resources (Roe and Aspinall, 2011). Recognising these benefits, the UK government has actively promoted walking through policy initiatives, including investments in pedestrian infrastructure, public awareness campaigns, and strategies to integrate walking into broader sustainable transport frameworks (Department for Transport, Active Travel England and The Rt Hon Mark Harper, 2023).

Existing studies suggest that walking behaviours are shaped by complex socio-economic, demographic, and spatial factors, yet many questions remain unanswered (Goodman, 2013; Zhao *et al.*, 2018). While previous transport studies have examined factors influencing travel mode choice (Hagenauer and Helbich, 2017), urban walkability and accessibility (Pereira, Vale and Santana, 2023), and the socio-economic inequalities in travel behaviours (Lucas *et al.*, 2016), this study specifically examines walking behaviours—participation and frequency—at a national scale (UK) over a 16-year period (2007–2023). By capturing long-term trends and the evolving impact of government policies on active travel, this research provides a comprehensive and policy-relevant analysis of the socio-economic determinants shaping walking behaviours. By analysing walking as both a necessity and a lifestyle choice, the research highlights its potential to reduce inequalities, enhance access to essential services, and support broader public health and environmental goals. The findings underscore the importance of sustained government investments and targeted interventions to position walking as a core component of equitable and sustainable transport systems.

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2. Dataset

The dataset for this study is derived from the National Travel Survey (NTS) (Department for Transport, 2024), an annual, nationally representative household survey conducted by the Department for Transport (DfT) to monitor long-term trends in travel behaviour in England. The NTS provides comprehensive data on individual travel patterns, including trip purposes, timing, transport modes, and key factors such as car availability and driving licence ownership. Data collection combines face-to-face interviews with a seven-day travel diary. The interviews capture demographic and socio-economic information, such as age, gender, socio-economic status, and car access, while the travel diary documents trip-level details, including transport modes, trip purposes, distances, and durations. This study focuses on walking behaviours recorded in the NTS, enabling an in-depth analysis of the socio-economic, spatial, and temporal factors influencing walking patterns. The integration of interview and diary data ensures a robust dataset for examining walking as a critical component of sustainable transport.

3. Methodology

This study employed a comprehensive methodological framework to investigate walking behaviours and their socio-economic determinants in England, incorporating descriptive analysis, regression modelling, and trend analysis. The descriptive analysis provided an overview of walking behaviours by examining participation and frequency across socio-economic and demographic subgroups, while visualisations highlighted key patterns and disparities.

To quantify the effects of socio-economic and demographic factors, two regression models were applied. Binary logistic regression was used to analyse walking participation (yes/no) and estimate odds ratios (ORs) for variables such as income, education, and car access. Zero-truncated Poisson regression modelled walking trip frequency, providing incident rate ratios (IRRs) for participants. Together, these models offered a detailed and robust understanding of the factors influencing walking behaviours. The final model specification was determined through a stepwise selection process, incorporating both forward and backward selection to ensure optimal model fit and interpretability.

4. Results

The analysis of walking participation rates from 2007 to 2023 (**Figure 1**) reveals an overall upward trend, with notable disparities across income quintiles. Higher-income groups consistently demonstrated higher walking participation rates, with the fifth quintile showing the most significant increase during the study period. In contrast, the lowest income quintile experienced slower growth, maintaining the largest gap in participation rates compared to wealthier groups.

Figure 1 Walking Participation Rate by Income Quintile (2007-2023)

Regression analysis further highlights the strong association between income and walking behaviours. Individuals in the highest income quintile were 39% more likely to participate in walking than those in the lowest. Similar trends were observed for walking frequency, with higher-income groups consistently reporting greater engagement. Gender and age differences were also evident, though less pronounced. Females were slightly more likely to walk than males, while individuals aged 30–64 exhibited higher walking frequency compared to younger adults, likely reflecting time constraints and lifestyle factors. Educational attainment emerged as another key determinant, with individuals holding formal qualifications being 21% more likely to walk. Mobility difficulties were significantly associated with lower walking participation and frequency, reflecting the physical challenges and accessibility barriers faced by individuals with impairments. The self-reported nature of mobility difficulties in the NTS suggests that these findings may reflect variations in perceived walking ability rather than absolute mobility limitations.

Geographical variations highlighted significant disparities in walking behaviours. Urban residents reported the highest participation rates, likely due to better public transport provision and more walkable urban form and amenities. Rural areas, in contrast, showed lower participation rates, reflecting differences in transport accessibility and mobility needs. Policy shifts, such as those during the COVID-19 pandemic, had a marked impact on walking behaviours, with increased participation observed across all income groups between 2020 and 2022. However, disparities persisted, underscoring the need for targeted interventions to support disadvantaged groups, such as investments in safe and accessible walking environments in low-income and rural areas.

5. Conclusion

This study examines walking behaviours in England, focusing on the socio-economic, spatial, and temporal factors influencing participation and frequency from 2007 to 2023. Overall, walking rates increased, with a notable surge during the COVID-19 pandemic, reflecting the impact of societal shifts on mobility patterns. Higher income, educational attainment, and urban residency were strongly associated with greater participation. While car access constraints reinforced walking as a key mode of travel for those with limited alternatives, individuals with mobility difficulties were significantly less likely to walk. Regional disparities emphasise the importance of targeted investments in walking

infrastructure, particularly in low-income and rural areas. The findings underscore walking's critical role as a sustainable transport mode and advocate for integrated policies to improve accessibility, equity, and public health outcomes. However, this study does not incorporate more advanced predictive models, such as machine learning, nor does it consider environmental factors like urban design, which may influence walking participation and frequency.

References

Department for Transport (2024) 'National Travel Survey, 2002-2023: Special Licence Access'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-7553-13>.

Department for Transport, Active Travel England and The Rt Hon Mark Harper (2023) 'Millions of people to benefit from £200 million to improve walking and cycling routes', 19 May. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/millions-of-people-to-benefit-from-200-million-to-improve-walking-and-cycling-routes>.

Goodman, A. (2013) 'Walking, Cycling and Driving to Work in the English and Welsh 2011 Census: Trends, Socio-Economic Patterning and Relevance to Travel Behaviour in General', *PLoS ONE*. Edited by H. Zhang, 8(8), p. e71790. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0071790>.

Hagenauer, J. and Helbich, M. (2017) 'A comparative study of machine learning classifiers for modeling travel mode choice', *Expert Systems with Applications*, 78, pp. 273–282. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2017.01.057>.

Lucas, K. *et al.* (2016) 'Modelling the relationship between travel behaviours and social disadvantage', *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 85, pp. 157–173. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2016.01.008>.

Pereira, M.F., Vale, D.S. and Santana, P. (2023) 'Is walkability equitably distributed across socio-economic groups? – A spatial analysis for Lisbon metropolitan area', *Journal of Transport Geography*, 106, p. 103491. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2022.103491>.

Roe, J. and Aspinall, P. (2011) 'The restorative benefits of walking in urban and rural settings in adults with good and poor mental health', *Health & Place*, 17(1), pp. 103–113. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2010.09.003>.

Weng, M. *et al.* (2019) 'The 15-minute walkable neighborhoods: Measurement, social inequalities and implications for building healthy communities in urban China', *Journal of Transport & Health*, 13, pp. 259–273. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2019.05.005>.

Zhao, C. *et al.* (2018) 'Urban form, demographic and socio-economic correlates of walking, cycling, and e-biking: Evidence from eight neighborhoods in Beijing', *Transport Policy*, 64, pp. 102–112. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2018.01.018>.

Biographies

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